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An invitation to unuttered rest //Performance at Sonic Territories 2021 July 1st to July 4th / 30min performance

“Human bodies are path-dependent, plastic, nonergodic, in short, historical. There is no true averaging of them” (Di Paolo et al., 2018).

Introduction

Move ---freely.

Move--- slowly.

Move----limited

This is an exercise on rest, but it is also an exercise in listening. We think of rest as static, still, silent.

But rest is also the possibility of allowing myself to be in listening, to find joy, and to discover new things in everyday life.

“Being-in-listening” is a closer approach to the self, meaning that “to be in listening is to be at the same time outside and inside” - to be open from the outside and from within. In a similar vein, Frantz Fanon emphasizes that “listening is not simply an act of consumption; it is a tactical expression of solidarity.”

*“Partir es morir un poco, llegar nunca es llegar definitivo”
–Oración del migrant*

For my participation in the Sonic Territories festival, I developed a sound exercise where we looked at small gestures of everyday life that allow us to make -space for listening to the city from within- as sonic soundspaces that already occupy our lives.

An Invitation to Unuttered Rest

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Exercise 1.

Listen to everything.

Notice everything.

Get a body sense of everything.

Play a tone or make a sound and/or movement.

Feel the weather against your skin.

How it settles you to the ground.

Say a word as a sound. Say a sound as a word.

What does it mean to be human in a world where everything could be “alive” and “a source” at the same time?

Listening is not only connected to sounds, but it is multisensorial, physical, and socially conditioned. The term *Urban Auscultation* is meant to acknowledge and center the symbiotic connections between our bodies and our cities, and how these connections are inherently unpredictable, fluid, and dynamic.

“Sonification asks us to extend our senses”

Exercise 2.

Redistribute your body weight.

Listen to your skin shift

Listen for a heart sound. (Affective)

Little by little – flex, strip skin back, allow subterranean organs to sit,

Exposed to the air. listen with your lungs, with the freshness of flesh, with your quivering liver. listen inward with your jaw - ear – along with bones, the plateau of skin. harking for back tremors, for that eyeball pulse.

Extend your biology –

Search for a pattern. Where does sound come from?

Where do you feel you have to be standing?

“Our most sophisticated knowing is full of uncertainty, inconsistencies, ambiguity, and contradictions [emphasis added]. These characterize how we most often deal with the world, ourselves, and each other”

Fixity has been crucial in the development of western science (Richard Lewontin, 1996), through history, western science has expanded and traced knowledge like a map that grows in complexity. In the practice of categorizing and dividing, we build borders in knowledge. The taxonomies often applied to knowledge create borders, often invisible, which might be likened to the "border-industrial complex" of the neoliberal nation-state. In the realm of automation, as in the nation-state, a particular theory of power is operative; it presumes that certainty can be engineered, and that fixity lies at the root of "fairness" (or efficacy).

Exercise 3.

Move ---freely.

Move--- slowly.

Move----limited

Go towards one of the shelves.

Track your sounds from left to right. Make sounds with objects of various kinds available, one alone, several together, on other instruments, sustained as well as short.

Is there any gap?

Locate the missing sound.

Trace with your fingertips the sound. Or hum continuously on a low note.

“The environment as a speaker”

Canto Cardenche originates in a profound way from the land. Indeed, it is the counteract to the dispossession of lands, to the discomfort and unsteadiness felt under the feet whilst transient. This state of transience brought a team of collaborators closer. Edna, Gil, Luisa, and I found each other in places that were difficult to call home while relying on screens and voice messages as our commonplace for the meeting. *I am my house, my many houses and in one of them, I find your voice* asserted Edna - we are all populated by different voices and our *bodies*, our territory. The ongoing, unscheduled exchange of voices, the glitches in communication, the city breathing in the background traced our experiences and relationships with the land each of us was situated in. In a way, we were “singing our maps” - mediating and mapping our relationships with our geographies through song.

Exercise 4.

Each participant explores a shelf from opposite sites. Find a sound that reminds you of a dream. Walk, play, stand, but remain in your opposites.

Now intently, trace a map of yourself. Take a rest and listen to the person on the other side. How does their sound compliments yours?

Each participant finds a way to enhance, nullify or otherwise interact with the sound or sounds that the group goes to hear.

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